

formation of pollen mother cells to the late uninucleate stage of pollen grains, were considered as sensitive to temperature. These stages occurred 9-19 d prior to heading (or 9-17 d after panicle initiation). Therefore, the critical temperature at which plants showed variation in pollen sterility and fertility was calculated by considering the average daily temperature and average maximum temperature prevalent during 9-19 d prior to heading.

Observations on the mean daily and maximum temperature during the sensitive stages of the identified TGMS lines indicated that these lines showed more pollen fertility when the mean daily temperature was $\leq 26^\circ\text{C}$, with a mean maximum temperature of $< 32^\circ\text{C}$. Similarly, a majority of the lines became male sterile when the mean temperature was $> 27^\circ\text{C}$, with a mean maximum temperature of $> 33^\circ\text{C}$. TGMS 6 (RP2161-106-1 S), TGMS 9 (mutant of IR50), TGMS 10 (C12 japonica purple S), TGMS 16 (IR68945-33-4-14-40 S), and TGMS 18 (IR68949 S) showed sterility-fertility changes under such temperature conditions. These lines showed high pollen fertility in December and January and pollen sterility in April and May. TGMS 16 and TGMS 18 remained pollen-free with empty anther sacs in the peak summer months, indicating the more stable nature of these lines. TGMS 18 remained pollen-free up to the first fortnight of June.

In November, TGMS 6 showed 25% pollen fertility at a mean daily temperature of 27°C and mean maximum of 31°C . When the mean daily temperature remained the same during March, but the mean maximum rose to 35°C , it showed 100% pollen sterility. This indicated the pronounced influence of maximum temperature on the sterility-fertility behavior of this line. For TGMS 18 also, the influence of maximum temperature became clearer, when the line showed 80% pollen fertility during September at a mean daily temperature of 27°C and maximum temperature of 32°C . The line turned out to be 100%

sterile when plants were exposed to the same mean daily temperature (27°C), but a higher maximum temperature (34°C).

These TGMS lines can be successfully used in two-line breeding by undertaking hybrid seed production programs in areas where constantly high temperatures (mean daily temperature $> 27^\circ\text{C}$, mean maximum temperature $> 33^\circ\text{C}$) prevail in the summer months. Similarly, these lines can be maintained at high-altitude areas where the temperature is low or even in the plains during December-January. ■

Hybrid rice research in Pakistan

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In Pakistan, hybrid rice research began in 1991-92. In evaluations made during 1992-95, IRRI hybrids outyielded local varieties KS 282 and IR6 by more than 50%. For practical exploitation of hybrid rice technology, local Basmati and non-Basmati germplasm is being converted into commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines. 17156A is the newly developed Basmati CMS line (male sterility source, IR58025A). Restorers are being identified for this line. Less restorer and higher maintainer frequency were observed in local germplasm. Therefore, $A \times R$ and $R \times R$ crosses are being made to increase restorer frequency. Maintainer frequency is being increased using $B \times B$ crosses. IR58025A, IR62829A, IR68897A, IR68896A, IR69617A, and 913A showed an excellent stigma exertion ratio, outcrossing rate, and other floral characteristics that influence outcrossing. One recessive gene for aroma and two dominant genes for fertility restoration of wild abortive cytoplasm were observed. Anther length and pollen grain size were observed to be monogenically controlled traits. Thermosensitive genic male sterility and the wide compatibility trait are being studied. Recently

developed hybrid IR58025A / KS 282 is being field-tested. Target areas for seed production are being located. Grain quality analysis shows that both parents should have acceptable grain quality to develop rice hybrids possessing that same quality. ■

Hybrid rice: status and future in Bangladesh

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The Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI) started hybrid rice research in 1993 through an informal collaboration with the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI). Initial work involved testing F_1 hybrids, and evaluating cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) and restorer lines received from IRRI. In CMS lines IR58025A and IR62829A, an outcrossing rate of 3% was recorded. The maintainers showed 80-90% spikelet fertility and a number of restorers were also identified. Some well-adapted varieties / lines were identified as maintainers or good restorers for the wild abortive cyto-sterility system. Some elite restorer lines are BR29, BR5876-6-2-1, BR4839-17-2-2-HR42, BR5690-62-23, BR5882-12-2-1 and BR5892-32-5-3. Some Chinese CMS lines and their maintainers were also evaluated for their adaptability and performance. These Chinese lines were not adapted to Bangladesh conditions and were highly susceptible to disease and insects.

A number of IRRI-developed hybrids were tested in multilocal yield trials during the 1995-96 boro season at Gazipur, Comilla, Bhanga, and Habiganj. A number of rice hybrids outyielded the standard check variety of the same duration by more than 1 t ha^{-1} . Grain quality characteristics of the tested hybrids were comparable with those of our recommended check varieties. These results have encouraged rice scientists and policymakers to develop and use hybrid rice technology in Bangladesh.

A working group for hybrid rice has been formed with a plant breeder, seed production specialist, and plant pathologist and entomologist. This program involves collaborative research with the Bangladesh Agricultural Develop-

ment Corporation, and other public and private agencies engaged in seed production in the country. A specific, time-bound, and goal-oriented work plan has been made for developing hybrid rice technology for the boro

season. Routine evaluation of elite lines and introduced rice hybrids is continuing. Four hybrid combinations were found promising and these hybrids are undergoing on-farm trials. ■

Grain quality

Donors for quality traits from the international aromatic nursery

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To identify some varieties with basmati background to be used as donors, the first International Fine Grain Aromatic Rice Observational Nursery (IRFAON), consisting of 33 entries including the international check Basmati 370 along with local check Pusa Basmati 1, was grown under normal cultural practices during the 1996 wet season. All the varieties were analyzed for 14 physicochemical characteristics at the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad, using standard procedures. These characteristics involve grain size and shape, endosperm appearance, and milling and head rice recovery (HRR). Among the cooking and eating quality traits, water uptake (WU), volume expansion ratio (VER), kernel length after cooking (KLAC), elongation ratio (ER), gelatinization temperature (GT), and amylose (AC) content were studied.

Of the entries tested, 22 belonged to long slender, 5 to long bold, 2 to medium slender, and 3 to short bold groups (Table 1) (see figure). In the long slender group, DR28 (7.38 mm), DR29 (7.37 mm), and Shah Pasand (7.35 mm) recorded high kernel length. Sixteen varieties showed >60% head rice, ranging from 60% (PK1656-48-2-2-1) to 69.7% (ARC11554). Among these entries, Basmati 385 and Shah Pasand exhibited high KLAC and ER, comparable with those of the checks. Basmati 385 recorded 14.5 mm KLAC and an

elongation ratio of 2.15 and Shah Pasand exhibited 14.2 mm KLAC and an elongation ratio of 1.93. Other entries that possessed moderate to high

KLAC combined with moderate ER were Binam, Domsiah, DR28, DR29, PK1379-9-1-1, PK1399-12-1-1, and Super Basmati.

Number of entries promising for key quality traits, 1996 wet season.

Table 1. Number of entries identified as promising for key quality traits, 1996 wet season.

Category	Number	Quality traits		
		Head rice recovery (>60%)	Intermediate gelatinization temperature	Intermediate amylose content (%)
Long slender	23	9	3	9
Long bold	5	3	1	4
Medium slender	2	2	1	1
Short bold	3	2	1	3
Total	33	16	6	17